

collagen, type II, alpha 1 (primary osteoarthritis,
spondyloepiphyseal dysplasia, congenital)
arthroophthalmopathy, progressive (Stickler syndrome)
(COL2A1) : Machine learning discoveries of 2nd order
synergy in Meningiomas

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Abstract

Background : COL2A1 provides instructions for the production of the pro-alpha1(II) chain of type II collagen. Type II collagen forms the basis for hyaline cartilage, including the articular cartilages at joint surfaces. It is implicated in Stickler syndrome, type II achondrogenesis-hypochondrogenesis, Spondyloepiphyseal dysplasias, osteoarthritis, chondrodysplasia, Kniest dysplasia, avascular necrosis of the femoral head and chondrosarcoma. However, its role in meningiomas has not yet been determined completely. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interations with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2nd order combinations of COL2A1, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might

*ML dicoveries of COL2A1 synergy in Meningiomas

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help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed by the search engine might pave way for development of gene based therapies aimed at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

Keywords: COL2A1, Meningioma, Sensitivity analysis, Machine learning.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective membranes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplastic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [3]). As of 2021, there exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp et al. [4]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angiomatous, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [5] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Württemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagiocephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossile, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [6], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecurtius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [7] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinhieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [12] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [8]. Finally, Cushing [9] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation. The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [10] and Pamir et al. [11]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. collagen, type II, alpha 1 (primary osteoarthritis, spondyloepiphyseal dysplasia, congenital) arthroophthalmopathy, progressive (Stickler syndrome) (COL2A1)

Strom et al. [13] prepared DNA from 39 human-mouse somatic cell hybrid lines, and mouse and human parental cell lines and was digested to completion with EcoRI and Southern filters were prepared. These filters were hybridized at high stringency conditions to the human genomic subclone pHCol(II) A which corresponded to the human α 1(type II) procollagen gene (COL2A1). It was observed that the mouse DNA yielded a single band at greater than 10 kb, whereas the human DNA had the expected single band at 4.8kb. Analyses of these human-mouse cell hybrids demonstrated that the human α 1(type II) procollagen gene segregates with chromosome 12.

Cheah et al. [14] identified the gene contained in the human cosmid clone CosHcol1, previously designated an α 1(I) collagen-like gene. They observed that CosHcol1 hybridized strongly to a single 5.9-kilobase mRNA species present only in tissue in which type II collagen is expressed. Their DNA sequence analysis showed that this clone is highly homologous to the chicken alpha 1(II) collagen gene. Their data suggested that CosHcol1 contained the human α 1(II) collagen gene COL2A1. The clone appeared to contain the whole gene (30 kilobases in length) and they hypothesized that it might be useful in the study of cartilage development and for identifying those inherited chondrodystrophies in which defects occur in this gene.

1.3. Roles of COL2A1 in different disease

The **Stickler syndrome** is an autosomal dominant hereditary disorder of connective tissue with pleiotropic features including premature osteoarthropathy, mild spondyloepiphyseal dysplasia, vitreoretinal degeneration, and the Pierre-Robin sequence. Franco-mano et al. [15] performed genetic linkage studies in two families with the Stickler syndrome using restriction fragment length polymorphisms associated with the structural gene for type II collagen, COL2A1. No recombinants between the Stickler phenotype and COL2A1 were observed. The total LOD score for linkage of the Stickler syndrome and COL2A1 at a recombination fraction (theta) of zero was 3.59. Their findings suggested that, at least in some families, the mutation causing Stickler syndrome affects the structural locus for type II collagen.

Godfrey and Hollister [16] extended the study of a mild case of **type II achondrogenesis-hypochondrogenesis** to include biochemical analyses of cartilage, bone, and the collagens produced by dermal fibroblasts. Type I collagen extracted from bone and types I and III collagen produced by dermal fibroblasts were normal, as was the hexosamine ratio of cartilage proteoglycans. Hyaline cartilage, however, contained approximately equal amounts of types I and II collagen and decreased amounts of type XI collagen. Two-dimensional SDS-PAGE revealed extensive overmodification of all type II cyanogen bromide peptides in a pattern consistent with heterozygosity for an abnormal pro α 1(II) chain which impaired the assembly and/or folding of type II collagen. This interpretation implies that dominant mutations of the COL2A1 gene might cause type II achondrogenesis-hypochondrogenesis. More generally, emerging data implicating defects of type II collagen in the type II achondrogenesis-hypochondrogenesis-

spondyloepiphyseal dysplasia congenita spectrum and in the Kniest-Stickler syndrome spectrum suggested that diverse mutations of this gene may be associated with widely differing phenotypic outcome.

Spondyloepiphyseal dysplasias (SED) are a heterogeneous group of inherited disorders characterized by disproportionate short stature and pleiotropic involvement of the skeletal and ocular systems. Evidence has suggested that SED might result from structural defects in type II collagen. To confirm the validity of this hypothesis, Lee et al. [17] examined the structure of the "candidate" type II collagen gene (COL2A1) in a relatively large SED family. Their coarse scanning of the gene identified an abnormal restriction pattern in one of the affected members of the kindred. Further, their analysis of selected genomic fragments, amplified by the polymerase chain reaction, precisely localized the molecular defect and demonstrated that all affected family members carried the same heterozygous single-exon deletion. As a consequence of the mutation, nearly 90% of the assembled type II collagen homotrimers were expected to contain one or more procollagen subunits harboring an interstitial deletion of 36 amino acids in the triple helical domain.

Ala-Kokko et al. [18] isolated a cosmid clone that contained an allele for the type II procollagen gene previously shown to be coinherited with primary generalized **osteoarthritis** in a large family. They observed that affected members of the family had evidence of a mild **chondrodysplasia**, but they developed progressive osteoarthritic changes in many joints that had no epiphyseal deformities. The mutation in the clone was found in all affected members of the family but not in unaffected members or in 57 unrelated individuals.

Kniest dysplasia is a moderately severe type II collagenopathy, characterized by short trunk and limbs, kyphoscoliosis, midface hypoplasia, severe myopia, and hearing loss. Mutations in the gene that encodes type II collagen (COL2A1), the predominant protein of cartilage, have been identified in a number of individuals with Kniest dysplasia. All but two of these previously described mutations cause in-frame deletions in type II collagen, either by small deletions in the gene or splice site alterations. Furthermore, all but one of these mutations is located between exons 12 and 24 in the COL2A1 gene. Wilkin et al. [19] used heteroduplex analysis to identify sequence anomalies in five individuals with Kniest dysplasia. They identified four new dominant mutations in COL2A1 that result in Kniest dysplasia, after sequencing of the index patients' genomic DNA, namely - a 21-bp deletion in exon 16, an 18-bp deletion in exon 19, and 4-bp deletions in the splice donor sites of introns 14 and 20. A previously described 28-bp deletion at the COL2A1 exon 12-intron 12 junction, deleting the splice donor site, was identified in the fifth case. Their data suggested that Kniest dysplasia resulted from shorter type II collagen monomers, and supported the hypothesis that alteration of a specific COL2A1 domain, which might span from exons 12 to 24, lead to the Kniest dysplasia phenotype.

Avascular necrosis of the femoral head (ANFH) causes disability that often requires surgical intervention. Most cases of ANFH are sporadic, but Liu et al. [20] identified three families in which there was autosomal dominant inheritance of the disease and mapped the chromosomal position of the gene to 12q13. They observed that in all patients with familial ANFH, carried COL2A1 mutations.

Chondrosarcoma is a heterogeneous collection of malignant bone tumors and is

the second most common primary malignancy of bone after osteosarcoma. Recent work had identified frequent, recurrent mutations in IDH1 or IDH2 in nearly half of central chondrosarcomas. Tarpey et al. [21] reported comprehensive genomic analyses of 49 individuals with chondrosarcoma (cases) and identified hypermutability of the major cartilage collagen gene COL2A1, with insertions, deletions and rearrangements identified in 37% of cases. They observed that the patterns of mutation were consistent with selection for variants likely to impair normal collagen biosynthesis.

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.4. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines has the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.5. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [22] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2nd order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [23] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, • linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option

has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references cited in Pujol et al. [23].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [24]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of formatting the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [25], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [22] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [22]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [26], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("extractMeningiomadata.R") • use source("manuscript-2-2.R") • use source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R").

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the non-linearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data

may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. COL2A1 related synergies

Note - COL2A1 was found to be upregulated in Type A. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and $FDR \leq 0.001$, in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 307 2^{nd} order combinations of COL2A1 were recorded.

3.1.1. COL2A1 - individual genes

The following genes in combination with COL2A1 showed high rankings - USH1 protein network component harmonin (USH1C), microsomal glutathione S-transferase 1 (MGST1), V-set and immunoglobulin domain containing 2 (VSIG2), tolloid like 1 (TLL1), mucolipin TRP cation channel 3 (MCOLN3), erb-b2 receptor tyrosine kinase 3 (ERBB3), calpain 6 (CAPN6), immunoglobulin superfamily member 9 (IGSF9), ATP binding cassette subfamily B member 1 (ABCB1), parathyroid hormone like hormone (PTH1H), tolloid like 2 (TLL2), neurotensin receptor 1 (NTSR1), mesothelin (MSLN), junctophilin 1 (JPH1), neurocalcin delta (NCALD), tight junction protein 3 (TJP3), glutamate ionotropic receptor kainate type subunit 5 (GRIK5), RUN domain containing 3B (RUNDC3B), cordon-bleu WH2 repeat protein (COBL), protein arginine methyltransferase 8 (PRMT8), peroxisomal biogenesis factor 5 like (PEX5L), interleukin 1 receptor like 1 (IL1RL1), melanophilin (MLPH), tetraspanin 1 (TSPAN1), phospholipid phosphatase related 4 (PLPPR4), periplakin (PPL), myelin regulatory factor (MYRF), proprotein convertase subtilisin/kexin type 2 (PCSK2), LIF interleukin 6 family cytokine (LIF), kallikrein related peptidase 8 (KLK8), proline rich and Gla domain 3 (PRRG3), microtubule associated scaffold protein 2 (MTUS2), brain expressed X-linked 2 (BEX2), kinesin family member 21A (KIF21A), SLAIN motif family member 1 (SLAIN1), ring finger protein 157 (RNF157), solute carrier family 47 mem-

ber 1 (SLC47A1), solute carrier family 44 member 3 (SLC44A3), cellular retinoic acid binding protein 2 (CRABP2), coiled-coil domain containing 150 (CCDC150), immunoglobulin superfamily member 11 (IGSF11), coiled-coil domain 39 molecular ruler complex subunit (CCDC39), serine protease 35 (PRSS35), astrotactin 2 (ASTN2), glycoprotein hormone subunit alpha 2 (GPHA2), calcium voltage-gated channel auxiliary subunit alpha2delta 1 (CACNA2D1), neural cell adhesion molecule 2 (NCAM2), solute carrier family 26 member 2 (SLC26A2), chloride intracellular channel 2 (CLIC2), glutamate receptor interacting protein 1 (GRIP1), SH3 domain containing ring finger 2 (SH3RF2), STEAP2 metalloredoxase (STEAP2), nucleophosmin/nucleoplasmin 2 (NPM2), actin alpha cardiac muscle 1 (ACTC1), angiotensin I converting enzyme (ACE), C3 and PZP like alpha-2-macroglobulin domain containing 8 (CPAMD8), cholinergic receptor nicotinic beta 2 subunit (CHRN2), cytochrome P450 family 3 subfamily A member 4 (CYP3A4), KIAA1522, Rho guanine nucleotide exchange factor 3 (ARHGEF3), sphingomyelin synthase 2 (SGMS2), solute carrier family 9 member B2 (SLC9B2), family with sequence similarity 160 member A1 (FAM160A1), ankyrin repeat domain 33B (ANKRD33B), STEAP family member 1 (STEAP1), adenylate cyclase 1 (ADCY1), lysine demethylase 1B (KDM1B), transient receptor potential cation channel subfamily V member 6 (TRPV6), phytanoyl-CoA 2-hydroxylase interacting protein like (PHYHIPL), protein phosphatase 1 regulatory subunit 36 (PPP1R36), calcium voltage-gated channel auxiliary subunit beta 2 (CACNB2), serine peptidase inhibitor, Kunitz type 1 (SPINT1), sodium voltage-gated channel beta subunit 3 (SCN3B), ubiquitin specific peptidase 54 (USP54), serpin family B member 8 (SERPINB8), pleckstrin homology domain containing A7 (PLEKHA7), alanyl aminopeptidase, membrane (ANPEP), myosin IA (MYO1A), small G protein signaling modulator 1 (SGSM1), OTU deubiquitinase 7A (OTUD7A), CDC42 binding protein kinase gamma (CDC42BPG), cilia and flagella associated protein 46 (CFAP46), interferon stimulated exonuclease gene 20 (ISG20), membrane bound glycerophospholipid O-acyltransferase 1 (MBOAT1), serine palmitoyltransferase long chain base subunit 3 (SPTLC3), bisphosphoglycerate mutase (BPGM), regulator of calcineurin 2 (RCAN2), carboxylesterase 4A (CES4A), ciliary microtubule associated protein 3/primary cilia formation (PIFO/CIMAP3), solute carrier organic anion transporter family member 2A1 (SLCO2A1), solute carrier family 35 member G1 (SLC35G1), family with sequence similarity 91 member A1 (FAM91A1), LRRN4 C-terminal like (LRRN4CL), G protein-coupled receptor 4 (GPR4), endoplasmic reticulum to nucleus signaling 1 (ERN1), WSC domain containing 1 (WSCD1), calpain 12 (CAPN12), coiled-coil serine rich protein 1 (CCSER1), MAF bZIP transcription factor F (MAFF), RNA binding motif protein 11 (RBM11), transcobalamin 2 (TCN2), insulin induced gene 1 (INSIG1), BCR activator of RhoGEF and GTPase (BCR), natural killer cell cytotoxicity receptor 3 ligand 1 (NCR3LG1), family with sequence similarity 78 member B (FAM78B), solute carrier family 6 member 9 (SLC6A9), laminin subunit beta 3 (LAMB3), AFDN divergent transcript (AFDNDT), SH3 domain binding glutamate rich protein like 2 (SH3BGRL2), ankyrin repeat domain 35 (ANKRD35), sterol regulatory element binding transcription factor 2 (SREBF2) and collagen type XV alpha 1 chain (COL15A1).

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I tabulate the rankings of 2nd order combination of COL2A1 with the above list, that were reported to be upregulated in Patel et al. [1]. Table 1 and 2 shows rankings of these combinations.

Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 3 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1 and 2.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS COL2A1									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T COL2A1									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
USH1C - COL2A1	300	290	284	280	MGST1 - COL2A1	169	192	212	6
VSIG2 - COL2A1	252	251	211	106	TLL1 - COL2A1	204	195	263	89
MCOLN3 - COL2A1	274	214	249	284	ERBB3 - COL2A1	278	211	267	221
CAPN6 - COL2A1	265	295	147	271	IGSF9 - COL2A1	212	269	305	16
ABCB1 - COL2A1	226	243	283	301	PTHLH - COL2A1	268	282	238	138
TLL2 - COL2A1	213	262	158	94	NTSR1 - COL2A1	236	212	288	180
MSLN - COL2A1	201	183	258	174	JPH1 - COL2A1	191	218	299	184
NCALD - COL2A1	163	190	252	17	TJP3 - COL2A1	193	206	213	24
GRIK5 - COL2A1	243	172	255	27	RUNDC3B - COL2A1	175	165	185	21
COBL - COL2A1	295	217	297	152	PRMT8 - COL2A1	266	221	275	282
PEX5L - COL2A1	258	261	221	62	IL1RL1 - COL2A1	229	268	208	287
MLPH - COL2A1	167	304	204	206	TSPAN1 - COL2A1	239	245	292	294
PLPPR4 - COL2A1	251	299	295	281	PPL - COL2A1	255	237	220	2
MYRF - COL2A1	195	293	202	279	PCSK2 - COL2A1	288	219	234	254
LIF - COL2A1	152	161	65	173	KLK8 - COL2A1	299	284	273	299
PRRG3 - COL2A1	210	205	290	198	MTUS2 - COL2A1	189	255	277	255
BEX2 - COL2A1	166	179	162	61	KIF21A - COL2A1	170	181	232	92
SLAIN1 - COL2A1	283	306	235	239	RNF157 - COL2A1	183	250	281	223
SLC47A1 - COL2A1	269	99	247	177	SLC44A3 - COL2A1	284	175	222	178
CRABP2 - COL2A1	203	197	280	160	CCDC150 - COL2A1	188	220	251	165
IGSF11 - COL2A1	224	266	226	194	CCDC39 - COL2A1	301	226	116	199
PRSS35 - COL2A1	304	240	296	215	ASTN2 - COL2A1	259	274	191	182
GPHA2 - COL2A1	298	300	279	115	CACNA2D1 - COL2A1	306	270	303	252
NCAM2 - COL2A1	228	207	168	151	SLC26A2 - COL2A1	250	152	216	67
CLIC2 - COL2A1	260	210	254	266	GRIP1 - COL2A1	233	231	301	195
SH3RF2 - COL2A1	256	244	231	183	STEAP2 - COL2A1	153	271	214	142
NPM2 - COL2A1	217	272	256	149	ACTC1 - COL2A1	253	287	261	207
ACE - COL2A1	151	113	274	209	CPAMD8 - COL2A1	199	173	178	34

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking between COL2A1 VS Individual members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 and 2 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t COL2A1 with COL2A1 – > USH1C / MGST1 / VSIG2 / TLL1 / MCOLN3 / ERBB3 / CAPN6 / IGSF9 / ABCB1 / PTHLH / TLL2 / NTSR1 / MSLN / JPH1 / NCALD / TJP3 / GRIK5 / RUNDC3B / COBL / PRMT8 / PEX5L / IL1RL1 / MLPH / TSPAN1 / PLPPR4 / PPL / MYRF / PCSK2 / LIF / KLK8 / PRRG3 / MTUS2 / BEX2 / KIF21A / SLAIN1 / RNF157 / SLC47A1 / SLC44A3 / CRABP2 / CCDC150 / IGSF11 / CCDC39 / PRSS35 / ASTN2 / GPHA2 / CACNA2D1 / NCAM2 / SLC26A2 / CLIC2 / GRIP1 / SH3RF2 / STEAP2 / NPM2 / ACTC1 / ACE / CPAMD8 / CHRN2 / CYP3A4 / KIAA1522 / ARHGEF3 / SGMS2 / SLC9B2 / FAM160A1 / ANKRD33B / STEAP1 / ADCY1 / KDM1B / TRPV6 / PHYHIPL / PPP1R36 / CACNB2 / SPINT1 / SCN3B / USP54 / SERPINB8 / PLEKHA7 / ANPEP / MYO1A / SGSM1 / OTUD7A / CDC42BPG / CFAP46 / ISG20 / MBOAT1 / SPTLC3 / BPGM / RCAN2 / CES4A / PIFO / SLCO2A1 / SLC35G1 / FAM91A1 / LRRN4CL / GPR4 / ERN1 / WSCD1 / CAPN12 / CCSER1 / MAFF / RBM11 / TCN2 / INSIG1 / BCR / NCR3LG1 / FAM78B / SLC6A9 / LAMB3 / AFDN-DT / SH3BGRL2 / ANKRD35 / SREBF2.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS COL2A1									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T COL2A1									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
CHRN2 - COL2A1	154	235	218	125	CYP3A4 - COL2A1	194	203	57	155
KIAA1522 - COL2A1	272	189	265	231	ARHGEF3 - COL2A1	289	258	196	163
SGMS2 - COL2A1	292	297	227	238	SLC9B2 - COL2A1	281	263	289	172
FAM160A1 - COL2A1	184	155	264	166	ANKRD33B - COL2A1	221	301	246	153
STEAP1 - COL2A1	280	273	180	119	ADCY1 - COL2A1	294	104	272	256
KDM1B - COL2A1	216	278	150	99	TRPV6 - COL2A1	277	294	223	110
PHYHIPL - COL2A1	227	135	188	171	PPP1R36 - COL2A1	190	164	206	158
CACNB2 - COL2A1	267	215	250	258	SPINT1 - COL2A1	303	233	287	247
SCN3B - COL2A1	275	283	173	82	USP54 - COL2A1	302	307	266	217
SERPIN8 - COL2A1	196	302	278	248	PLEKHA7 - COL2A1	181	264	245	234
ANPEP - COL2A1	257	157	228	218	MYO1A - COL2A1	241	208	230	109
SGSM1 - COL2A1	238	200	224	246	OTUD7A - COL2A1	270	291	286	203
CDC42BPG - COL2A1	143	194	229	204	CFAP46 - COL2A1	249	248	298	220
ISG20 - COL2A1	197	176	194	202	MBOAT1 - COL2A1	262	213	291	167
SPTLC3 - COL2A1	232	180	270	257	BPGM - COL2A1	291	281	257	272
RCAN2 - COL2A1	307	230	302	241	CES4A - COL2A1	164	246	241	156
PIFO - COL2A1	305	193	244	175	SLCO2A1 - COL2A1	174	153	152	69
SLC35G1 - COL2A1	248	296	268	212	FAM91A1 - COL2A1	214	292	129	169
LRRN4CL - COL2A1	264	249	271	108	GPR4 - COL2A1	223	229	276	123
ERN1 - COL2A1	293	253	307	240	WSCD1 - COL2A1	286	178	294	164
CAPN12 - COL2A1	273	277	285	201	CCSER1 - COL2A1	282	265	184	77
MAFF - COL2A1	177	234	239	98	RBM11 - COL2A1	271	303	243	131
TCN2 - COL2A1	165	275	304	260	INSIG1 - COL2A1	279	305	306	277
BCR - COL2A1	205	169	248	193	NCR3LG1 - COL2A1	254	223	236	200
FAM78B - COL2A1	219	298	151	191	SLC6A9 - COL2A1	179	267	181	161
LAMB3 - COL2A1	287	288	201	148	AFDN-DT - COL2A1	235	241	293	170
SH3BGRL2 - COL2A1	182	289	262	143	ANKRD35 - COL2A1	237	163	240	233
SREBF2 - COL2A1	297	280	237	230	- COL2A1				

Table 2: 2nd order interaction ranking between COL2A1 VS Individual members.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic COL2A1 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of COL2A1-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t COL2A1	
USH1C / MGST1 / VSIG2 / TLL1 / MCOLN3 ...	
ERBB3 / CAPN6 / IGSF9 / ABCB1 / PTHLH ...	
TLL2 / NTSR1 / MSLN / JPH1 / NCALD / TJP3 ...	
GRIK5 / RUNDC3B / COBL / PRMT8 / PEX5L ...	
IL1RL1 / MLPH / TSPAN1 / PLPPR4 / PPL ...	
MYRF / PCSK2 / LIF / KLK8 / PRRG3 ...	
MTUS2 / BEX2 / KIF21A / SLAIN1 / RNF157 ...	
SLC47A1 / SLC44A3 / CRABP2 / CCDC150 ...	
IGSF11 / CCDC39 / PRSS35 / ASTN2 / GPHA2 ...	
CACNA2D1 / NCAM2 / SLC26A2 / CLIC2 / GRIP1 ...	
SH3RF2 / STEAP2 / NPM2 / ACTC1 / ACE / CPAMD8 ...	
CHRNA2 / CYP3A4 / KIAA1522 / ARHGEF3 / SGMS2 ...	
SLC9B2 / FAM160A1 / ANKRD33B / STEAP1 / ADCY1 ...	
KDM1B / TRPV6 / PHYHIPL / PPP1R36 / CACNB2 ...	
SPINT1 / SCN3B / USP54 / SERPINB8 / PLEKHA7 ...	
ANPEP / MYO1A / SGSM1 / OTUD7A / CDC42BPG ...	
CFAP46 / ISG20 / MBOAT1 / SPTLC3 / BPGM ...	
RCAN2 / CES4A / PIFO / SLCO2A1 / SLC35G1 ...	
FAM91A1 / LRRN4CL / GPR4 / ERN1 / WSCD1 ...	
CAPN12 / CCSER1 / MAFF / RBM11 / TCN2 ...	
INSIG1 / BCR / NCR3LG1 / FAM78B / SLC6A9 ...	
LAMB3 / AFDN-DT / SH3BGRL2 / ANKRD35 / SREBF2	COL2A1

Table 3: 2^{nd} order combinatorial hypotheses between COL2A1 and Individual members.

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Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

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